

A Study on the Opinion of Monpa Community Parents of Arunachal Pradesh towards Formal Education

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Abstract

This study examines the opinion of Monpa Community parents towards formal education in Tawang and West Kameng districts of Arunachal Pradesh. Using a self developed opinionnaire and a descriptive survey method data were collected from 400 parents. The opinionnaire consisted of 23 items with scores ranging from 23 to 115. The computed mean score of 103.50 and standard deviation of 8.82 indicates a highly favourable parental opinion towards formal education, far above the average score of 69. Findings suggest that while monasteries were once the primary centers of learning, formal education has gained strong acceptance among the Monpa community. They have recognised modern schooling as a means of cultural and socio-economic advancement.

Keywords

Monpa Community, Parental Opinion, Arunachal Pradesh, Tribal Education.

Introduction

Education plays a crucial role in modern, industrialized society. It is essential for individuals to receive quality education in order to thrive in today's competitive world. A well-educated society consists of individuals with high living standards and knowledge, enabling them to develop effective solutions to challenges. Education significantly influences a person's life by shaping their thoughts and mindset. It assists students in planning for their future studies and helps individuals think, feel, and behave in ways that promote personal and societal success. Furthermore, education fosters personality development, enhances critical thinking, and prepares individuals for various life experiences. Without education, a person may struggle to survive and secure a respectable position in society. Education provides guidance in decision-making, helping individuals make informed choices. Ultimately, being educated allows a person to contribute meaningfully to the community, making it an honorable pursuit. Education is a fundamental need not just a desirable accessory. Education goes beyond academic achievement, imparting valuable life skills, character, and a sense of unconditional love and moral values. Most profoundly, it teaches us the value of unconditional love and a strong moral compass. Education is a life long journey of growth and self discovery, where we learn from diverse experiences perspectives and people. Education is a continuous process of learning, growing and self-improvement, shaping us into the person we are meant to be.

A Brief Profile of Arunachal Pradesh:

Arunachal Pradesh is the 24th state, located in the country's easternmost region, covering an area of 83,743 square kilometers. It lies between latitudes 26° N and 29° N and longitude 91° E and 97° E. The state shares its borders with Bhutan to the West, Tibet and China to the North, Myanmar to the East and Assam and Nagaland to the South. Arunachal Pradesh had population of 1,383,727 as per 2011 census, spread across 26 towns and 3,863 villages. It is home to 26 major tribes and over 100 sub-tribes, each with its unique culture traditions and way of life. Among the prominent tribes are Adi, Monpa, Apatani, Galo, Nyishi, Tagin, Nocte, Khampti, Singpho, Sherdukpen, Wangcho. The Monpa tribe is primarily found in two districts-West Kameng and Tawang. These districts are located in the western part of Arunachal Pradesh, with Tibet to the north, Assam's Darrang and Sonitpur districts to the south, East Kameng to the East, and Bhutan to the West. Together, these districts span an area of 9,594 square kilometers. The Monpas are further categorized into three groups based on their geographical locations: Dirang Monpa (central), Tawang Monpa (Northern), and Khalaktang Monpa (Southern). The Tawang Monpas mainly inhabit the Tawang district, whereas the Dirang and Khalaktang Monpas are spread across the West Kameng district, alongside other indigenous tribes. Among the Monpas, Tawang Monpa is numerically the largest amongst them. According to 2011 Census, Tawang district records a population of

49, 977 and West Kameng district records 83,947, out of which, Dirang as a population of 18401, Khalaktang 6622, Thembang 1,334, and Balem 816 (areas habituated by Monpas under West Kameng).

The study focuses on two districts of Arunachal Pradesh: (a) Tawang and (b) West Kameng district.

Objective of study

To find out the opinion of parents of Monpa community in Tawang and West Kameng districts towards formal education.

Review of Literature

Samal (2012) assessed the attitude of parents towards education and schooling of their children. The findings showed that the overall attitude of the respondents was moderately favorable and positive towards schooling and education of their children. There was no significant difference in the attitude of tribal and non-tribal parents. Gender difference was also found to be non-significant. The research suggested that, although government endeavors at universalizing education has resulted in increasing mass awareness and positive response towards schooling and education, there is a lot of scope for improvement in this regard.

Bordhan (2014) assessed the attitude of parents towards schooling of their children from 145 parents basically tribal from Assam. The study found that the overall attitude of the respondents was moderately favourable and positive towards schooling and education of their children. the study suggested that there is lot of scope for improvement universalization of education and creating mass awareness and positive response towards education.

Ceka and Murati (2016) conducted a study on the role of parents in education of children, the study found that the family plays a crucial role in shaping a child's education, personality and overall development. Parents significantly influence their children's intellectual, moral, and social growth through every day interactions and family activities. A positive and supportive home environment helps children develop good values, disciplined behaviour, and a healthy attitude towards learning.

Jafari and et al (2024) conducted a study on impact of parents' attitude on children academic performance and the finding of the study revealed that parents' positive attitude and active coordination with teachers significantly improved children's academic performance at the primary level. It also revealed that parental support was stronger in private schools, and regular parent-teacher meetings played a key role in enhancing students' motivation, discipline, and achievement.

Main Text

Significance of the Study:

Education is one of the most powerful instrument for social change, cultural preservation, and economic development. Despite significant progress in expanding educational opportunities across India, disparities in access, participation, and perception of education continue to exist among tribal communities. The Monpa community of Arunachal Pradesh, traditionally rooted in monastic and cultural learning, has gradually embraced formal education.

Parents play a crucial role in shaping a child's educational aspirations and motivation. Their opinion towards formal education directly influences enrollment, retention, and performance in schools. Yet there is limited empirical research that systematically examines how Monpa parents perceive formal education.

Therefore, the present study seeks to examine the opinion of Monpa community parents towards formal education using self developed opinionnaire. It aims to understand whether their attitudes are favourable, neutral or unfavourable.

Methodology

A descriptive survey method was adopted for the study. A self developed opinionnaire on parental opinion towards formal education was administered to sample of 400 parents from Tawang and West Kameng districts of Arunachal Pradesh. The tool consisted of 23 items, and the maximum possible score was 115, with a minimum of 23. The obtained data were analyzed using mean and standard deviation.

Findings

The computed mean score of parental opinion was 103.50, with a standard deviation of 8.82. The average or mid-point score of the opinionnaire was 69. The obtained mean score (103.50) is significantly higher than the average score, indicating a highly favourable parental opinion toward formal education. The result suggests that parents of Monpa community are aware of the importance of formal education and hold positive and supportive attitude toward schooling.

Conclusion

The study concludes that the Monpa community, despite its strong traditional and religious background, has shown a positive transition toward embracing formal education. The high mean score of parental opinion reflects growing awareness of education's role in socio-economic and cultural advancement. Further the parents

have understood the importance of education in shaping the all round development of their children.

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